

The first trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.

D6.5 Dissemination toolkit and project's website

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Glossary and Abbreviations	
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
MS	Microsoft
EU	European Union
M	Month

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Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to communicate to stakeholders in Africa and Europe information about the project's activities, events and achievements; to disseminate the project's results widely and beyond the borders of the AfriConEU partnership including to other EU and Africa countries, by involving other networks and projects to which the partners belong or are affiliated with. Deliverable 6.1 (Communication and Dissemination plan) includes the creation of the visual identity and brand framework of the project including: Website, Project logo, Standards manual, Social Media, Pitch Desk, Presentation template, Letterhead, Word Deliverables template, E-mail signature, Leaflet.

1. Website

A web page was developed at <https://africoneu.eu/>. The website was released on Month 2 of the project (one month earlier than planned). It is intended to be the main point of information for anybody interested in the project, and will publish up-to-date information about the project and its activities, along with the deliverables.

The structure of the website is the following:

Home: main entry point. It has the vision of the project, along with the, a call to join the newsletter the project and the newsletter.

Figure 1 - Website/ Home page

Footer: There is a common footer in all pages of the website where someone can check latest videos of AfriConEU YouTube channel, last Instagram posts and last Tweets of each respective AfriConEU social media.

Figure 2 - Website/Social Media Footer

Additionally, as required per Article 29.41 of the Grant Agreement, all material used for communication and dissemination purposes of AfriConEU, will demonstrate the EU emblem along with the statement that the project has received funding from the H2020 Research and Innovation programme and that this website reflects only the author's views and the Research Executive Agency or European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Figure 3 - Website/ EU emblem footer

About us: Main information about the project, solution, methodology, phases of the project, its vision and objectives, partners and Advisory Board.

Figure 4 - Website/ About us page

Networking Academy: Main information about the Networking Academy of AfriConEU and its three main categories (DIHs Capacity, Transcontinental partnership, AfriConEU Online Community).

Figure 5 - Website/ Networking Academy page

Platforms: This section includes the Agrifood Cooperation platform by our partner ITC - INOVACIJSKO TEHNOLOSKI GROZD MURSKA SOBOTA and AfriConEU e-learning platform.

Figure 6 - Website/ platforms page

Join: This section includes a call for people to join AfriConEU depending on the category they belong.

Figure 7 - Website/ Join page

Library: This section includes gallery, scientific publications, training resources, public deliverables of AfriConEU.

Figure 8 - Website/ Library page

What's new: News, Press Clips and Newsletters of the project. This section will fulfil a double function: providing updates on the project, publishing interesting and relevant content to generate engagement and, accordingly, helping to boost the SEO in relation to certain terms.

Figure 9 - Website/ What's new page

Contact us: A contact form for those interested in receiving more information or would like to contact us for any reason.

Figure 10 - Website/ Contact us page

Part of the website, it will host publications on project deliverables and meetings, and important milestones. Events attended will also be displayed in the what's new section, provided that the responsible partners write a short post for themselves or provide Youthmakers Hub with a detailed account of the events and some good pictures.

The Privacy Policy, together with the Terms and Conditions have also been included in the AfriConEU website, set for the general rules and policies governing the visitors' use of the website.

2. Project Logo

AfriConEU logo was created using the project acronym as the main element and a number of circles and lines that form the shape of Africa's map. Since AfriConEU aspires to become the first Trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European Digital Innovation Hubs, this is depicted with lines and circles connecting African countries, thereby representing a robust digital network. Thus, formal typography was selected and rounded for a softer effect. The EU is bold and deep blue, the same colour with the dots to depict the interaction and sharing of knowledge between the two continents. Blue is used as a base colour as it is associated with technology and innovation. Deep blue is used to indicate confidence, reliability, and responsibility.

Figure 11 - AfriConEU Logo

Figure 12 - AfriConEU Logo Black & White

White and black versions of the logo have been developed to be used over coloured backgrounds. The AfriConEU logo has been developed in all formats in RGB and CMYK in EPS, JPEG, PDF and PNG formats and have been uploaded in the Microsoft Teams folder shared to all partners. All partners can find all formats of the logo in the MS folder. There are different

formats for digital use and printing use of the logo, partners should pay attention to that and should contact Youthmakers Hub for any doubt regarding the logos.

3. Standards Manual

A standards manual has been created for AfriConEU providing the colour palette of the project and the fonts used. Partners can find the Standards Manual in the MS folder.

Figure 13 - Standards Manual

4. Social Media

AfriConEU project has established (M2) social media account for Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, Instagram and YouTube, according with the proposal description. Some hashtags, which are being used for the AfriConEU project, are the following: **#AfriConEU**, **#DIH**, **#H2020**, **#EUAfrica** and **#AfricaEurope**.

A [linktree account](#) has been created for the project, so all social media are gathered in one page and in this way, it is easier to promote all of them at once.

Figure 14 - Linktree page

4.1 Facebook page

AfriConEU's Facebook page will focus at establishing direct communications with target audiences, other relevant groups individuals, including DIHs & other audiences' segments.

Figure 15 - Facebook page

4.2 Twitter account

Figure 16 - Twitter account

An AfriConEU twitter account will be used for amplifying communications to a large community of active stakeholders. In order to reach more audiences, there has been created a database of accounts to be tagged in relevant posts to increase the visibility of the page.

4.3 LinkedIn page

An AfriConEU LinkedIn page will be used for amplifying communications to a large community of active stakeholders, as well as for propagation of news and project developments. Regular LinkedIn post will focus at attracting and engaging with target audiences leading also to the establishment of a trusted AfriConEU network, enlarging the outreach to broad and targeted audiences.

Figure 17 - LinkedIn page

4.4 Instagram page

Figure 18 - Instagram page

An AfriConEU Instagram page will be used for amplifying communications to a large community of active individuals (entrepreneurs, innovators, startups), DIHs, networks and similar initiatives and projects, as well as for propagation of news and project developments.

4.5 YouTube channel

An AfriConEU YouTube channel will be used for sharing all videos that will be created in the framework of the project.

Figure 19 - YouTube channel

5. Pitch Desk

AfriConEU will be presented in several events, conferences meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results, enhancing the overall dissemination efforts. For that reason, a pitch desk presentation has been developed so all partners can use it to present the project in any occasion that may arise.

Figure 20 - Pitch Desk Sample

6. Presentation Template

AfriConEU PowerPoint presentation templates will be presented in several events, conferences, meetings as well as other occasions to disseminate project developments and results, enhancing the overall dissemination efforts. A presentation template (ppt) has been designed in line with AfriConEU graphic identity in order to promote the recognition of AfriConEU.

Figure 21 - Presentation Template

Additionally, as required per Article 29.41 of the Grant Agreement, all material used for communication and dissemination purposes of AfriConEU, will demonstrate the EU emblem

along with the statement that the project has received funding from the H2020 Research and Innovation programme.

7. Letterhead

A letterhead was developed for online and offline use by all partners. Partners can find the letterhead in the shared MS folder. Partners are advised to download the file to use it.

8. Word Deliverables Template

Figure 8.1

The AfriConEU deliverable template was produced in line with the overall communication and dissemination material graphic identity and will be used by the consortium partners for the development of all project deliverables. The deliverable template has a cover page that displays the project’s logo in a prominent position, its acronym, deliverable information (number, full title, the work package number and title) as well as the writers information. Partners can find the Word Deliverables Template in the shared MS folder. Partners are advised to download the file to use it.

Figure 22 - Word Template for Deliverable

9. E-mail Signature

E-mail signatures were designed for two members of INOVA+ and the Dissemination Manager of AfriConEU. Partners can find the letterhead in the shared MS folder.

Figure 23 - E-mail Signature

10. Leaflet

A project was developed with key points about the project and relevant information (targeted to the main audiences). The leaflet is translated in English, Greek, Italian, Portuguese and Slovenian (main languages of the project). There are two formats for the leaflet, one for digital use and one for printed use. Partners can find the leaflet in the shared MS folder.

Figure 24 - Leaflet